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Forage crop improvement: Conventional and novel methodologies

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Livestock rearing is an integral part of the various farming systems in India and has been a major source of employment in rural areas for centuries. Its share is 4.4 per cent to the Gross Value Added of the agriculture and allied sector. The area cultivated under fodder amounts to 4% of the total cultivable area in India. There is tremendous pressure on available feed and fodder by livestock, as land available for fodder production is decreasing. Greater focus being given towards productivity enhancement in the recent years, it becomes all the more essential for ensuring the availability of quality feed and fodder to sustain higher productivity in animals. This can be achieved through forage breeding *viz.*, conventional, biotechnological and molecular approaches by which cultivars with high and sustainable herbage yield under various management systems can be developed. Although new technology may be used to create and introduce new genetic variation into breeding pools, much of its subsequent use will be by conventional breeding. Research tools in structural and functional genomics promise to explore the underlying genetics, physiology and biochemistry of many complex plant processes and thus speed-up progress in applying gene technology-based approaches to forage plant improvement. Under-exploited wild plants, grasses, legumes and trees have a tremendous potential to be used as forage and can be cultivated easily in homesteads. Thus, there is a great scope to increase forage productivity by strengthening the genetic improvement activities, exploring the possible breeding strategies to meet the demand-supply gap in fodder.

Keywords: Conventional Methodologies, Forage Crop Improvement, Novel Methodologies